

$20 \pm 0.1^\circ$. For titrations, a number of solutions containing calculated amount of rare earths in 0.1 mol dm^{-3} KCl as supporting electrolyte were prepared. pH of the test solutions was adjusted to 6.5 ± 0.02 using dilute HCl/NaOH solutions, on a Elico L1-120 digital pH meter.

Results and Discussion

Naphthalein scarlet-4RS gives a well defined cathodic reduction wave. The height of the diffusion current is proportional to the concentration of the dye.

The plateau potential of naphthalein scarlet-4RS - 0.90 V (vs Hg-pool), at which rare earths do not give any wave, was applied. A standard solution of rare earth was added dropwise from a semimicro burette. The current was noted on the multiflex galvanometer after each addition of the rare earth aliquot. On plotting a graph between galvanometer deflection and added titrant volume (after necessary volume correction), a L-shaped curve was obtained. The end-point of titration indicated metal to ligand ratio of 1 : 1, which is in good agreement with the results reported in the literature¹. Reversed L-shaped curves may be obtained by choosing naphthalein scarlet-4RS as titrant.

It was observed that 100-fold concentration of ions, i.e. Na^+ , K^+ , NH_4^+ , chloride, chlorate, nitrate, acetate and sulphate do not interfere in the titration procedure. However, a small amount of Ag^+ , Bi^{3+} , Al^{3+} , Fe^{3+} , VO^{2+} , MoO_4^{2-} , and carbonate ions interfere with the titration seriously.

Ultramicro and microgram quantities of La, Ce, Pr, Sm, Nd, Er, Tb, Gd and Dy have been separately estimated amperometrically, with in an error of less than $\pm 0.8\%$.

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Studies on Macroreticular Cation-exchangers

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ION-EXCHANGERS are generally manufactured from various organic chemicals and hence, there is an increase in the cost of these materials. In order to minimise the cost of the chemicals as well as the cost of ion-exchangers, various materials¹, like rice husk², bagasse³ and coconut fibre⁴ etc., were converted into charcoal in our laboratory. The present work is an attempt to prepare cation-exchangers with charcoal obtained from groundnut shells.

Experimental

Phenol and formaldehyde (B.D.H.) and concentrated sulphuric acid (sp.gr. 1.82) were used. Groundnutshell procured locally, was powdered and cleaned before use.

Phenol (10 g) and concentrated H_2SO_4 (12.5 ml) were mixed slowly with constant cooling and then heated to about 100° on a water-bath for 3 h, cooled immediately in ice and kept overnight.

Sulphonated groundnut charcoal was added to phenol-sulphuric acid mixture so as to keep the percentage of substitution of groundnut shell charcoal at 0, 20, 25, 30, 35, 40, 45, 50 and 100. Each mixture was polymerised with formaldehyde (12.5 ml) at 70° to yield a reddish brown powder, which was grounded, sieved and preserved for further work. These constitute the samples labelled A, B, C, D, E, F, G, H and I.

The average swelling percentage and the absolute density are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—PERCENTAGE SWELLING AND ABSOLUTE DENSITIES

Sample no.	Percentage of groundnut shell charcoal in resin	Average swelling percentage	Absolute density	
			In the hydrated state	In the dehydrated state
A	0	80.40	1.48	1.37
B	20	76.50	1.47	1.36
C	25	75.40	1.40	1.35
D	30	74.80	1.38	1.35
E	35	73.50	1.37	1.27
F	40	70.90	1.31	1.17
G	45	68.40	1.30	1.15
H	50	67.80	1.21	1.11
J	100	49.00	1.15	1.10

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The percentage swelling in water indicates certain rigidity in the matrix of the resin as well as of samples. From the absolute density of the various samples (Table 1) the packing nature of the samples are revealed. The density measurements indicate the inherent porosity of the samples and so these may be useful in non-aqueous solvents.

The exchange column capacities for the exchange of Na^+ (0.1 M), Ca^{2+} (0.1 M), Zn^{2+} (0.1 M) on the H^+ -form of the ion-exchangers are presented in Table 2.

The exchange capacity as determined by EDTA titrations for $\text{Ca}^{2+}/\text{Zn}^{2+}$ are found to be higher than that of Na^+ . Further, it is observed (Table 2) that there is a continuous decrease in exchange capacity of composites and the fall is not much upto 20% of groundnut shell charcoal in the resin. Thus the substitution of groundnut shell charcoal upto 20% is economical since the exchange capacity of the composite is acceptable.

TABLE 2—EXCHANGE CAPACITY OF H^+ -FORM OF COMPOSITES

Sample no.	Percentage of groundnut shell charcoal in resin	Exchange column capacity (Estimated)		
		Na^+ (0.1 M)	Ca^{2+} (0.1 M)	Zn^{2+} (0.1 M)
A	0	0.910	1.432	1.356
B	20	0.853	1.412	1.304
C	25	0.789	1.319	1.268
D	30	0.784	1.300	1.288
E	35	0.738	1.284	1.140
F	40	0.718	1.268	1.048
G	45	0.694	1.214	0.983
H	50	0.688	1.128	0.875
I	100	0.450	0.954	0.754

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